

A preliminary analysis of the unexplored Great Chamber in the Great Pyramid

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Abstract

In 2022, Filippo Biondi and Corrado Malanga published *Synthetic Aperture Radar Doppler Tomography Reveals Details of Undiscovered High-Resolution Internal Structure of the Great Pyramid of Giza* [1], which revealed the network of passages and rooms yet to be explored in the Great Pyramid. One particular room is very large, close to the north face, and may be what the less-precise Scan Pyramids project detected as a large void [2].

Even though we do not yet have access to this room, the published dimensions are enough to “reverse-engineer” the likely internal dimensions. As with everything about Giza and the Great Pyramid, the room appears to be a mathematical *tour de force* like the King’s Chamber, including the usual π , φ^2 , and e . These numbers, all over Giza, continue to challenge the historical time-line.

Keywords: Giza, Great Pyramid, History of Mathematics, π , φ , e .

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“All is number.”

Pythagoras

“The language of Giza is mathematics.”

Robert Bauval

1 Introduction

Biondi and Malanga’s (B&M) innovative research [1] reveals the internal structure of the Great Pyramid, as shown in Figure 1. This current paper is a speculative analysis of the Great Chamber (Green Room) above the ascending passage. Using B&M’s published dimensions, which are the external dimensions for the room (*Dr Malanga, pers. comm.*), and allowing for walls, floor and ceiling, lets us hypothesize the likely internal dimensions. It turns out that the dimensions are in fact based on Douglas Rectangles (*The Douglas Triangle, Prime Roots, and e* [3]), and the particular size chosen provides more mathematical fun.

Figure 1: Khufu interior, looking from east. [1]

Since both the King’s Chamber and the Queen’s Chamber are replete with mathematics, we can logically assume that this chamber is too, and use that knowledge to guide the analysis. When in doubt, look for what makes mathematical sense.

These are thus my predictions about how the room will look, and as such, a test of how well I understand the mindset of the designers.

2 The usual irrationals

Certain numbers keep popping up at Giza. I call these “their favourite numbers”. The list includes π , φ , φ^2 , e , c , $\sqrt{2}$, $\sqrt{3}$, $\sqrt{5}$, 1.87, and 137. Since the use case was construction, they used practical approximations. They used 3.1416 for π when needed, but were happy to approximate that to simpler versions like 3.14 or 3.142 when showing intent rather than exactitude was sufficient. Even today, we still use $\frac{22}{7}$ or 3.14 in school. Similarly with the other irrationals.

Symbol	Name	“Full” value	Practical value	Practical % Accuracy
π	Archimedes’ constant	3.1415926...	3.1416 or 3.142 or 3.14	99.9998, 99.9870 or 99.9493
η	Eagle’s constant ($\frac{\pi}{2}$)	1.570796327...	1.5708 or 1.571 or 1.57	99.9998, 99.9870 or 99.9493
e	Euler’s number	2.7182818...	2.7183 or 2.718 or 2.72	99.9993, 99.9896 or 99.9368
φ	Golden ratio	1.61803398...	1.618 $\varphi + 1 = \varphi^2 = 2.618$	99.9979
ρ	Plastic ratio	1.32471795...	1.3247 $\rho + 1 = \rho^3 = 2.3247$	99.9986 or 9.9458
\mathcal{C}	Royal cubit	0.5236 m	From $\frac{\pi}{6}$ or $\frac{\varphi^2}{5}$, rounded	
ϑ	Thoth’s Constant ($\frac{\pi\varphi}{e}$)	1.87000613...	1.87	99.9997

Table 1: Symbols, names and values

I use “cubit” for the Royal cubit (G). Other researchers use other values, but 0.5236 m works for me.

We are familiar with the cubit divided into 28 digits. However, Petrie (§141) (*The Pyramids and Temples of Gizeh* [4]) had trouble getting 28 digits to add up to one cubit, and instead found evidence (§139) that the builders used a decimal cubit. Petrie is a little vague here, it looks like he is suggesting a cubit divided into 10 rather than 28. My own investigations show that what works is a cubit divided like a modern metre stick, into 100 centicubits (cG) and 1000 millicubits (mG). This provides a very accurate way to measure, since each division is about half a millimetre. Figure 2 shows a comparison between metric and cubits.

Figure 2: Centimetres and millimetres compared to decimal centicubit and millicubit divisions.

Assume we need to measure 12.56 cG (0.1256 G). The 12.5 part is easy and can be read off the ruler. We would need to interpolate the 0.06 part, which is $\frac{6}{1000}$ of 1 G, or about 0.3 mm. The question then arises, can we cut a stone block to that precision? Or build two walls a given distance apart to that precision, which will withstand the ravages of thousands of years? We need to look beyond raw measurements, however accurate, and look at what the intended dimensions were.

This problem affects the analysis, as things are sometimes close without being exact. For example, $\frac{40}{2.618}$ is 15.27883881, but we can not build to that precision, so we round to 15.2788, which is already challenging. Then 15.2788×104.72 is 1599.995936, while $15.27883881... \times 104.72$ is 1600.0000

Equations shown below may use a science/engineering approach, not pure mathematics, so $1.999 = 2.0$.

We are dealing with a different culture, which may have had a different approach to accuracy and precision, compared to our modern scientific mindset. My Giza analysis suggests they typically worked to 3 or 4 decimal places. This may indicate that they used abacuses or counting tables, or possibly slide rules or logarithms, to calculate. Alternatively, they may just have used four decimals as anything more did not make sense in construction. 0.0001 G is 0.05236 mm, which is about 50 microns, half the smallest distance that can be seen with the naked eye, and approaching the length of a human liver cell.

When we sent the Pioneer plaques [5] into space, we made certain assumptions about the life forms that might one day discover them. In the same way, the Giza designers had to make certain assumptions about who would one day decipher their messages built in stone. So some things may be over-simplified, or alternatively, we are not at the same as level they were in certain fields. One example would be the Golden Ratio... it is all over Giza, but hardly used in our mathematics and science.

I make no apologies for the metre. While the 4th dynasty did not use it, whoever built Giza appears to have been familiar with it, or something very close to it. Various things around Giza only make sense when considered in metres rather than cubits, some of which will be discussed below in Section 7.

3 The language of Giza is mathematics

Robert Bauval’s aphorism is the key to Giza. Distances are not just distances, but messages from the past. Whoever designed Giza clearly loved mathematics, perhaps even on the level of religion.

Just about everything used a recurring set of numbers, including those shown in Table 1. By way of example, here are a few diagrams from previous papers, showing how these numbers occur. I’ll show a few from the site plan, and then several from the King’s Chamber, since we will discuss how the Great Chamber does similar things. I’m only showing the existing three pyramids rather than the full site plan (*Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [6]).

Source papers include *Zep Tepi Mathematics 101* [6], *The Consequences of Legon’s Rectangle: The Rational Giza Design* [7], *The Writing is on the Wall: The King’s Chamber Game* [8], *Observations on the King’s Chamber Dimensions* [9], and *Khufu’s Coffin* [10].

3.1 The site plan

Figure 3: Mathematical site design

Figure 4: Plenty of π @ 3.14

Figure 5: Multi-tasking: It all works together.

3.2 The King's Chamber

Figure 6: Main horizontal patterns

Figure 7: Main vertical patterns

Figure 8: φ

Figure 9: Vertical double square

Figure 10: Pythagorean 3-4-5 triangle

Figure 11: Metres and cubits

The diagonals of the long walls are $5\sqrt{21}$ G, effectively 12 metres (11.997 m). The chamber design is the most sensible and practical way to achieve an “integer” length in metres.

The chamber height, from floor to ceiling, is $\sqrt{125}$ G, which is effectively 11.18 G. We could also write this as $\sqrt{5^3}$, $(\sqrt{5})^3$, or $5\sqrt{5}$.

The diagonal of the short walls is effectively 15 G. The distance from any corner to the one opposite, in 3-D space, is 25 G, or 5^2 G

The diagonal of the floor or ceiling, is $10\sqrt{5}$ G.

The visible area of the long walls is $100\sqrt{5}$ G².

The visible area of short walls is half that of the long walls, i.e. $50\sqrt{5}$ G².

The volume of the chamber is 2236 G³ = $1000\sqrt{5}$.

3.3 The Coffin

Figure 12: The coffin

I included these examples to demonstrate the builders' familiarity with various mathematical and scientific constants and concepts, which, according to the historical time-line, they were not supposed to know. The evidence disputing that claim is rock solid.

4 Calculating the internal dimensions

Biondi and Malanga provide two diagrams with the chamber dimensions, as shown in Figures 13 and 14.

Figure 13: Top view of the chamber.

Figure 14: Side view of the chamber.

There are two different values for the width, 22.914 m and 23.498 m. After playing around with possibilities, I decided that 23.498 m worked better. That gives us 56.772 × 23.498 × 9.43 m as exterior dimensions. At that point I converted to royal cubits (C) by dividing by 0.5236, giving 108.426 × 44.88 × 18.01 C.

We now have to make reasonable allowances for the walls, ceiling and floor, to get the internal dimensions. After some experiments, I settled on 2.44 C (1.278 m) thickness for the long walls, and 1.853 C (0.97 m) thickness for the short walls. The long walls will be supporting the ceiling slabs, so it is appropriate to make them sturdier.

That gives a width of 44.88 – (2 × 2.44) = 40 C, and a length of 108.426 – (2 × 1.853) = 104.72 C. The outer dimensions and wall thicknesses are approximate, what is important is the inner dimensions. Dr

Malanga (*pers. comms.*) indicated a possible error of up to 1.6 metres in any given dimension. The internal dimensions conform to the Douglas Rectangle shape, where the length is 2.618 times the width.

The Douglas Triangle, (discussed *The Douglas Triangle, Khufu and Khafre* [11]) can be made into a rectangle by joining two triangles. Figure 15 shows the result with the Great Chamber dimensions, and the King's Chamber for comparison. This helps put the large size in perspective.

Figure 15: Great Chamber floor

For the height, I tried various likely candidates, including 16.18 (10ϕ), 15.71 ($\frac{10\pi}{2}$), and 11.18 ($\frac{10\sqrt{5}}{2}$) cubits, but nothing would work, until it was revealed to me (“obvious and logical”) that the short walls are also Douglas Rectangles. So that made the height $\frac{40}{2.618} = 15.2788$ \mathcal{G} . This is exactly 8 metres. It also possibly suggests that the walls have 8 courses of blocks, each one metre high. For comparison, the courses in the King's Chamber are 1.17 m high on average. The difference to 18 \mathcal{G} is about 2.731 \mathcal{G} , so I assigned 1 \mathcal{G} to the floor, and 1.732 (i.e. $\sqrt{3}$) \mathcal{G} to the ceiling slabs.

The internal dimensions are thus $104.72 \times 40 \times 15.2788$ \mathcal{G} . We can also write that as $40\phi^2 \times 40 \times \frac{40}{\phi^2}$. If we use h for the height, then height : width : length are in the ratio $h : h\phi^2 : h\phi^4$.

The dimensions are summarised in Table 2, and illustrated in Figure 16.

Item	Length	Width	Height
B&M metres (1)	56.772	22.914	
B&M metres (2)		23.498	9.43
Used dimensions metres	56.772	23.498	9.43
Used dimensions \mathcal{G}	108.426	44.88	18.01
Derived internal dimensions \mathcal{G}	104.72	40.00	15.2788
Derived internal dimensions m	54.831	20.944	8.00
Walls \mathcal{G}	2.44	1.853	
Walls m	1.278	0.97	
Floor \mathcal{G}			1.00
Floor m			0.5236
Ceiling \mathcal{G}			1.732
Ceiling m			0.9069

Table 2: Summary of dimensions

When I began the analysis, I assumed that the chamber was built with red Aswan granite, like the King's Chamber, due to the large floor plan, impressive height, and possible long ceiling spans. As things progressed, it became clear that instead of granite, it was actually dressed in white Tura limestone, like the Queen's Chamber. So I illustrate the chamber with white walls where possible and keep the B&M-inspired green where needed for contrast. Section 5 includes reasons why it has to be Tura.

Figure 16: Great Chamber interior shape

5 Ceiling and internal structure

Initially I thought the Great Chamber was one large, extremely impressive open chamber. While dealing with practical issues like the ceiling slabs, and following the mathematics, it became clear that it was subdivided into 16 smaller chambers, each 25 by 9 Ɔ. For comparison, the King's Chamber is 20 by 10 Ɔ. This section explains how I got to that design. There is nothing comparable that we know of in any other pyramid.

5.1 Long walls

The Grand Chamber is forty cubits wide, which is nearly 21 metres. B&M's diagrams indicate a flat ceiling like the King's Chamber, rather than gabled like the Queen's Chamber. That creates a practical problem for the ceiling beams, since 21 metres is very long. Cleopatra's Needle in New York is 21 m of Aswan granite and weighs 200 tons. One solution would be to use shorter beams about the same length as the King's Chamber, and have one or more internal walls running the length of the room to support them.

If we want them about the same length as the King's Chamber, we will need to have three internal walls, spaced about about 9 to 10 Ɔ apart. Alternatively, we need beams twice as long as the King's Chamber, and one long internal wall.

Instead of a wall, it may be possible to use pillars, but that has the side effect of forcing the beams to be wider to leave space between the pillars. If the pillar has a 1 Ɔ diameter, the slabs will need to be at least 2 cubits wide, to allow a 1 Ɔ space between the pillars. This is rather cramped. If we want 2 Ɔ (about 1 metre) between the pillars, then the slabs will need to be about 3 Ɔ wide. That gives a volume of say $21 \times 3 \times 1.732 = 109 \text{ Ɔ}^3$, or 15.66 m^3 , which is a rather heavy 42.457 metric tonnes each [12]. Limestone can be as heavy as granite, depending on the variety. Tura limestone is finer and denser than the Mokattam limestone used for the bulk of the pyramid (*Performance of some commercial consolidating agents on porous limestones from Egypt* [13]).

After exploring various options, I decided to take the most practical approach with three internal walls. The mathematics that followed from that suggests that it is probably correct. I set the spaces between the walls to be each 9 Ɔ wide, for a total of 36 cubits. That leaves 4 cubits for three walls, which I divided with the centre at 2 Ɔ and the other two at 1 Ɔ each.

Practically, this allows for either ceiling beams about the same length as in the King's Chamber, each spanning 9+ Ɔ, or 20+ Ɔ beams, running from the wide centre wall to the sides, and supported by the thinner walls. This arrangement also supports a mathematical reason, shown later.

Figure 17 shows the view from the East, using Wikipedia's diagram as background. The Queen's Chamber northern shaft may be too long here.

Figure 17: Great Chamber location with internal and external walls. Background image from Wikipedia[14]

As illustrated, the passage and floor of the King's Chamber is at a distance of $\frac{280}{\sqrt{2}} = 198 \text{ G}$ from the top. The Queen's Chamber passage, and thus the original floor, is similarly $\frac{280}{\sqrt{\phi}} = 238.51 \text{ G}$ from the top.

It seems likely that the Great Chamber is at a distance of $\frac{280}{\sqrt{\pi}} = 191.18 \text{ G}$ from the top. This may be slightly lower than shown in B&M's diagrams, but it is difficult to get the exact height from the 3D perspective, and that particular dimension is not given. The north-south location is as per their diagrams, but it can't go higher because it would move outside. The location also contradicts the idea that Khufu as it is now was an enlargement of a smaller pyramid.

5.2 Short walls

Dr Malaga (*pers. comm.*) indicates that they believe that the Queen's Chamber northern air shaft goes through the Great Chamber, as shown in Figure 17. The only way to do this sensibly would be for there to also be short internal walls in the chamber, and for the shaft to run inside one of these walls.

The Djedi Project explored the Queen's Chamber shafts in great detail. To integrate their results, I used five resources: Petrie's [4] measurements for the height of the entrance and horizontal part, Smyth's [15] diagrams for the east-west location of the entrance, Matt Sibson's video *First Look Inside the Great Pyramid Queen's Chamber Northern Shaft* [16], Keith Payne's report (which Wikipedia cites as the official report), *The Djedi Project: The Next Generation in Robotic Archaeology* [17], and Stefan Bergdoll's paper *Die Dixon-Relikte und die Geheimnisse der kleinen Schächte der Cheopspyramide* [18].

It seems that Petrie-level accuracy about the lengths, twists and turns in the shaft was not part one of the project requirements. So we have some vague measurements, including distances possibly rounded to the nearest foot, and angles given as "about".

Sibsen's birds-eye diagram of the shaft (Figure 18) shows the shaft heading off at an angle of 5° west of north, which I find to be uncharacteristic of the builders. He gets this by having a left turn of 45° , followed by two right turns of 20° . However the actual text does not support that exactly, apart from the initial 45° left turn.

Figure 18: General path of QC north shaft
[16]

The following extracts from Bergdoll are translated by Google Translate (first and third), and Philipp Kiefer (second).

Bergdoll quotes one comment by Zahi Hawass, as follows: “During our exploration of the Northern Shaft (QCN), the robot ascended approximately 19 meters (60 FEET), and turned through the sharp Left (West) bend. NEXT FOLLOWED two shallow right turns (to the East at 22 meters (75 FEET) and 25 meters (83 feet)). This may reorient the shaft to its original direction to the North.”

Bergdoll writes, “According to an article by Zahi Hawass, there are bends in the northern shaft at 23.16 m and 25.60 m (both towards the right) and one at 29.26 m back towards the left. Relative to the bend at 18.14m, the sections between the bends are 5.02 m, 2.44 m and 3.66 m long. Interestingly, Hawass published completely different figures nine years later, partly contradicting those published earlier.”

Another explanation from Hawass is, “To summarize its findings: At 23 meters (76 feet) the shaft bends to the right at an angle of approximately 20 degrees (Fig.9). At 25 meters (84 feet), there is another turn to the right at approximately the same angle. At 29 meters (96 feet), the shaft bends slightly to the left (Figs 10, 11 and 12).”

Higher up there appears to be slight bend to the right again.

If, for example, the first bend to the right was 21 or 22 degrees, and the second 22 or 23, then we are close to being back on a path supporting the original comment of “This may reorient the shaft to its original direction to the North.” It is worth noting that the King’s Chamber northern shaft also bends before resuming a path due north.

The top section of the shaft is built with a better quality limestone, presumed to be Tura. The same occurs at the top of the southern shaft. This suggests to me that the shaft is running inside a wall of the Great Chamber, which in turn implies that the Great Chamber is dressed in white Tura limestone like the Queen’s Chamber, and not granite like the King’s Chamber.

I decided to have three short internal walls, because that leads to interesting mathematics, as well as providing a set of rooms about the same size as the King’s Chamber. The total chamber length is 104.72 ƒ, suggesting 4 divisions giving a small room length of 25 ƒ, and 4.72 ƒ for the three walls, which is about 1.57333 ƒ each, or about $\frac{\pi}{2}$ ƒ each, given construction tolerances. For reasons shown later, I sized the centre wall at 1.58ƒ, and the other two at 1.57ƒ each.

That division, combined with the similar divisions for the long walls, gives us 16 rooms, each 25 ƒ by 9 ƒ.

Figure 19: Chamber with internal walls

The view from the front or north is shown in Figure 20. The Queen’s Chamber northern shaft is approximate. It ends a little lower than in Figure 17, so either my calculations are wrong or the Wikipedia author did not take the side bends into account and used the raw length.

Figure 20: Great Chamber location from north.

I plotted the Queen’s Chamber northern shaft by starting with data from Petrie and Smyth, then using the precise metre measurements from Hawass (second extract above), with angles of 45°, 22°, and 23°. That nicely aligns it closely with the pyramid centre. It also means that the shaft is curving, not to AVOID something as commonly speculated, but to align itself with the centre wall in the Great Chamber. The actual purpose of these shafts is still a mystery.

6 The entrances

B&M’s diagrams (Figures 13 and 14) show the entrance passages to be about 2.456m wide, and 3.178m high. This translates to about 4.69 G wide and 6.07 G high. While these are the “outer dimensions,” they are considerably more comfortable for humans than the typical 2 G square shafts elsewhere in the pyramid. The actual passage dimensions will be less.

If the courses in the Great Chamber are 1 metre high, then setting the height at 2 metres seems reasonable. This is the same height range as modern standard doors, which vary around this value by country [19].

For the width, reducing it to 2.0944 m or 4 G produces good results. These are discussed in Section 7.

From measuring B&M’s diagram, it looks like the eastern passage enters the Great Chamber on the eastern side of the short internal wall. The western passage is less clear, it may also be east of the dividing wall, but I went for a symmetrical approach and put it on the western side.

Both the King’s Chamber and Queen’s Chamber have their entrances next to a wall. This design idea continues in modern homes ... entrances to private spaces like bedrooms are next to walls, while entrances to public spaces like sitting rooms or kitchens are more flexibly spaced.

The entrances are illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Great Chamber entrances.

A possible arrangement of inter-room connections is shown in Figure 22. I have kept them all at 4 \mathcal{G} , in case the builders needed to manoeuvre large objects between the rooms.

The Queen's Chamber Northern shaft runs through the south end of the middle wall, which excludes having a doorway there.

Figure 22: Possible inter-connections between the rooms.

7 The mathematics in the design

There are different ways to explore the mathematics built into the design. We can look at the outer chamber while ignoring the internal rooms, look at the dimensions of the internal rooms, look at the walls, or do more complex operations with selected walls and rooms.

As a reminder, the cubit:metre ratio is 0.5236:1. Multiples of that ratio pop up a few times.

Some numbers appear frequently in religious texts. These include 3, 7, 12, 40, and 144. We have already seen 40 as the width, it is used in more places. There are also examples of 3.

Common themes in the mathematics include π , φ^2 , perfect squares, and interplay between cubits and metres.

We start with the complete chamber, as if the internal walls and rooms did not exist.

7.1 The complete chamber

Figure 16 above shows the Great Chamber gross dimensions, $104.72 \times 40 \times 15.2788$ cubits.

104.72 is 2×52.36 .

The ratio of long wall to short wall is $\frac{\text{length}}{\text{width}} = \frac{104.72}{40} = 2.618$, by design.

The area of a long wall is $15.2788 \times 104.72 = 1600 \mathcal{G}$, a perfect square.

The volume of the entire chamber is $1600 \times 40 = 64000 \mathcal{G}^3$, a perfect cube. A sphere with the same volume would have a radius of 12.9926 metres... this is close to 13 in the same way that the diagonal of the long wall in the King's Chamber is close to 12 m.

So we have a progression: width of short wall is $40 \mathcal{G}$ (1 dimension), area of long wall is $1600 \mathcal{G}^2$ (2 dimensions), and volume of room is $64000 \mathcal{G}^3$ (3 dimensions), each step with a constant multiplier of $40 \mathcal{G}$. The volume is the cube of the short wall.

Figure 23: Comparing areas

The area of the chamber, divided by the area of the contained circle, is $\frac{104.72 \times 40}{3.1416 \times 20^2} = 3.333\bar{3}$.

7.2 The small rooms

Figures 19 and 21 show the chamber with the internal walls.

Each small room is $25\text{c} \times 9\text{c}$. Each length is a perfect square.

The floor area of each room is $25 \times 9 = 225 \text{c}^2$, also a perfect square.

In metres², it is 61.685316m^2 . That is $\left(\frac{31.416}{4}\right)^2$.

There are 16 rooms, again a perfect square, and completing the Pythagorean $3^2 - 4^2 - 5^2$ sequence.

The total floor area of the 16 rooms is $16 \times 25 \times 9 = 3600\text{c}$, again a perfect square.

In metres², that is 986.965056m^2 , which is 31.416^2m^2 .

A square with that area would have a side of 60c , which is 31.416m .

A circle with that area would have a radius of 17.72455923m , which is $\sqrt{314.16}$.

The room height is $\frac{40}{2.618} = 15.2788$.

The volume of each small room is $15.2788 \times 25 \times 9 = 3437.73$.

In metres³, that is $\frac{(10\pi)^2}{2} \text{m}^3$.

Converting to metres³ requires multiplying by 0.5236^3 , which we can write as $\left(\frac{\varphi^2}{5}\right)^3$.

The full calculation can be written

$\frac{40}{\varphi^2} \times 25 \times 9 \times \left(\frac{\varphi^2}{5}\right)^3$, which simplifies to $2^3 \times 3^2 \times \varphi^4 \approx \frac{(10\pi)^2}{2}$.

A sphere with the volume of a small room would have a radius $\frac{3\sqrt[3]{157.08}}{4} \text{m}$. 157.08 is $\frac{100\pi}{2}$.

The area of the short wall is $\frac{40 \times 9}{2.618} = 137.5095493$, which is equal to the Golden Angle.

Figure 24: Circle divided in Golden Ratio

The area of the long wall is $\frac{40 \times 25}{2.618} = 381.9709702$, i.e. $\frac{1000}{2.618}$. This is 104.72m^2 , numerically the same as the length of the Great Chamber in cubits.

The entrance passage at 4 G allows a progression of squares, in keeping with the all the other perfect squares in the design.

Figure 25: Entrance room squares: $2^2, 3^2, 4^2, 5^2, 6^2$

The entrance passage is 2m high, which is $3.8197 G$, the inverse of 0.2618 , keeping with our theme of φ^2 . Furthermore, the cross-section of the entrance passage is $4 \times 3.8197 = 15.2788$, numerically the same as the chamber height.

7.3 The walls

7.3.1 Euler’s number e

Figure 26 shows the Great Chamber and short walls, together with the underlying irrational dimensions. These are scaled by $40 G$ for the chamber dimensions.

Figure 26: An excellent e approximation

The imaginary diagonal of the room is $\sqrt{104.72^2 + 40^2} = 112.0994134G$.

There are three internal short walls, and two outer short walls, each $40G$ long. Their total length is $200G$.

Then $\frac{\text{long wall} + 5 \text{ short walls}}{\text{diagonal}} = \frac{104.72 + 200}{112.0994134} = 2.7183$. (*The Douglas Triangle, Prime Roots, and e* [3])

As shown in that paper, the underlying irrational version produces a very good approximation for e .

$$\frac{\text{blue}}{\text{red}} = \frac{\varphi^2 + 5}{\varphi\sqrt{3}} = 2.71828280782816535616\dots$$

$$2.71828280782816535616 - e = 0.000000979369120\dots$$

$\frac{\varphi^2 + 5}{\varphi\sqrt{3}}$ can also be written as $\sqrt{15} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$, or $\sqrt{3}\sqrt{5} - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}$. This brings in some of their favourite square roots, which are otherwise missing in this analysis. See the paper for the proof.

7.3.2 Pi

There are three internal long walls, each $104.72G$ long. Their total length is $314.16G$.

7.3.3 The cubit

There are five long walls in total. Their total length is $523.6G$, which is $104.72\varphi^2 m$.

7.4 Rooms and walls

7.4.1 The speed of light

The Great Chamber provides an excellent approximation for the speed of light in M€ or Mm. It is simply the sum of each set of lengths of the small rooms (red lines), without the centre dividing wall, plus the four total widths (blue lines), illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Speed of light

This is by far the best reference to the speed of light by the Great Pyramid. Table 3 is an updated version of the summary table in *Another reference to the speed of light by the Great Pyramid* [20].

Method	Value	Difference	Comments
c	299 792 458.0		
Latitude	299 791 670.0	788.000	Depends on Globe model, continental drift
Circles full values	299 795 759.8	3301.872	
Circles rounded values	299 787 346.0	5112.116	
$\log_{1.618} \vartheta$	299 789 329.7	3128.287	
Great Chamber	299 792 416.0	42.000	

Table 3: References to speed of light by Great Pyramid

299.792458 Mm converts to 572.5600802 M€, and it is not possible to measure the “...00802” part without a microscope, let alone build to that tolerance. So this reference to *c* is the best possible.

7.4.2 The inverse of the Fine Structure Constant α

The convenient inverse to the Fine Structure Constant α , 137, appears frequently at Giza. The Great Chamber also provides a reference to that value, illustrated in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Inverse of Fine structure Constant α

8 The contents

What could be in this chamber, if it has not already been looted?

Egyptologists hope for Khufu’s body or grave goods.

I hope for large volumes of documents sharing their knowledge. Perhaps some products of their civilisation.

Perhaps there will be nothing but exquisitely made granite boxes like at the Osireion, sealed and empty. We need to measure these carefully, the message is in the dimensions.

9 Conclusion

After I was shown the Douglas Triangle linking Khufu and Khafre's base sizes (*The Douglas Triangle, Khufu and Khafre* [11]), I got to wondering why, if it was such an important triangle, it was not used elsewhere at Giza. I was then advised that it actually was. So I stared at the site map but could not find it. I asked, "where?" The answer was, "in the Great Pyramid." Which also made no sense, as I was familiar with the known internals, and that triangle is not there. Then Biondi and Malanga's paper came along, and I was attracted to the Green Room. Once I started looking at it closely, I realised what the dimensions were implying and I was flabbergasted...

That solved the puzzle of where else that triangle was used, and once again I had to eat humble pie and stop being such a Doubting Thomas. It's my natural scepticism against far-fetched claims, and very annoying when the claims turn out to be correct, however unlikely they appeared in the beginning.

So once again we have Mathematics in Stone, where the sharing of knowledge is done via means that are hard to casually destroy. It is just a matter of realising that there is more going on than an empty chamber and sarcophagus.

It is such a pity that Egyptologist refuse to look at this evidence objectively. Apparently prevailing religious beliefs in Egypt dictate a given time-line, and anything that challenges that time-line is simply ignored or dismissed as "co-incidence". How many π ratios does it take to convince someone that either Giza is not 4th dynasty, or if it is, then the history of mathematics is wrong? If Giza is not 4th dynasty, then when was it built?

If my analysis of this unexplored Great Chamber is even partially correct, then we have more clear evidence of the builder's familiarity with π , φ , and e , and possibly c and α .

Perhaps the block patterns on the walls have another story to tell, like in the King's Chamber (*The Writing is on the Wall: The King's Chamber Game* [8]).

This chamber may be the real treasure in the Great Pyramid. Certainly, given it's size and complex structure, it must have had a special purpose. Now we just need to find a way to get inside and explore... hopefully with television cameras so that everything is recorded.

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